

**THE ANALYTIC USAGE OF PSYCHOLOGIC METHODS IN
LANGUAGE TEACHING (PSYCHOLINGUISTICS ANALYSIS OF THE
SEMANTICS OF THE NOMINATIVE UNITS OF THE TEXT)**

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Annotation: As an approach, there are several methods that have been developed based on the theories of psycholinguistics and these methods are widely used in the field of language teaching in different countries. Some species method will be explained in this article. To avoid misunderstanding, some terms related to psycholinguistics, the study and teaching of languages are also explained in this article.

Keywords: psycholinguistic approach, methods, suggestopedia, natural method, total physical response method.

Language perception refers to listening and reading, and language production refers to speak and write. Listening, reading, speaking and writing are called the four language skills. In particular, psycholinguistics helps to understand the difficulties of these four skills inherent in both difficulties and external difficulties. Psycholinguistics also helps explain the mistakes students make in language learning. In addition, psycholinguistics also defines certain types of brain disorders that affect the effectiveness of language learning, such as agraphia and aphasia, which must be treated properly.

The approach considers language and thought as related, but completely independent phenomena. Education is considered as an individual cognitive process that occurs within the individual, and then turns into a social measurement.

Psycholinguistics as a science of the psychology of language is realized in language teaching which helps study the psychological factors that may be associated with language learning. Psycholinguistics focuses on the application of

actual language and communication. A decision needs to be made in the application of various methods that allow students to easily understand the language.

The method is a fundamental implementation of the approach. The creators of the method came to decisions about the types of activities, the roles of teachers and students, the types of material that will be useful, and some model for organizing the curriculum. Methods include various procedures and techniques such as part of their standard rate. Methods of teaching the language of the psycholinguistic approach are also important in acquisition of second language. The approach to language learning consists of theories of the nature of language and theories language learning. Language teaching methods are a specification of approaches to language teaching.

A language teaching method can be well understood if its fundamental theories are clearly understood. There are three fundamental theoretical views on the development of language teaching methods: structural theory, functional theory and interaction theory. Structural theory considers language as a system of grammatical units: phrases, sentences, sentences, affixes, etc. Functional theory considers language with its function as a means of communication: informational, emotional, persuasive and social. Interactive

The theory considers language as a means of implementing interpersonal relationship and as a means of social interaction and transactions between the individual and society. Each point of view influences development differently.

Psycholinguistics was used widely as a fundamental theory in the development of a language teaching method. Some of the methods that have been developed on the basis of a psycholinguistic approach are described as follows:

1. Natural Method. This method believes that language learning is a reproduction of the way humans naturally acquire their native language. This method rejects earlier methods such as the audiolingual method. Psycholinguistic principles in language learning according to this method are as follows.

- a. Language mastery relies on learning language skills in a natural context and less on conscious learning of grammatical rules.

b. Learning a language is an effort to develop communicative competence, the ability to understand the speech of native speakers and native speakers understand the learners' speech without any error which can interfere with meaning.

c. Comprehension is primary than production.

d. The model that underlies this method is five monitors theory: (1) acquisition learning hypothesis, (2) natural order hypothesis, (3) monitor hypothesis, (4) feedback hypothesis, (5) affective filter hypothesis.

The consistency of this method is shown by natural technique developed by teacher.

Teacher stimulates the learners to competence activity such as problem solving, game, and humanistic affective. Problem solving is designed to train learners to find out a right situational answer or solution. Games are considered as an interlude activity, but it is designed to improve students' language competence. humanistic affective is designed to implicate opinions, feelings, ideas, and reactions to language learning activity.

2. Total physical response method. Language competence will be greatly improved through the involvement of kinesthetic sensory system in language learning. This is due to the fact that children are given statements that require them to move physically. Understanding is primary, not the production of speech. Students are sent to achieve comprehension competencies before they attempt to speak or write. In connection with kinesthetic theory, it is believed that there is a positive correlation between physical movements and language achievements of students. It becomes the focus of design and application of appropriate language teaching techniques in a particular topic.

This method requires a spacious class. The class ideally consists of 20-25 students. This method can be used to teach children or adults. Grammar rules are presented in the imperative mood, because basically all materials are presented in the imperative mood offers. A dictionary is not needed in this method because the

meaning of the words will be expressed in physical activity. Students usually don't get homework because the language learning takes place together in the classroom.

3. Suggestopedia. The psycholinguistic principles of language learning by this method are as follows.

1. People can be made to do something by creating a relaxed atmosphere for them and open and calm mind. This will stimulate the nerves to respond easily and keep information longer.

2. Before class begins, students are encouraged to relax their bodies and minds to acquire hypermnesic abilities, this is an incredible super-memory.

3. The classroom is dimly lit, comfortable chairs, relaxed atmosphere and classical music.

4. Laboratory program and strict grammar exercises in class are rejected.

Each meeting in this method is divided into three time slots. First considers the previous topic through discussion, games, sketches or role plays. If students do some mistakes, the teacher carefully corrects them to maintain a positive atmosphere. The second one is distributing traditional dialogue. The third relaxes the students. It is divided into two parts: activity and passive activity.

In conclusion, I would like to point out that psycholinguistics has provided many theories to explain how a person acquires a language, produces and perceives both oral and written speech. Theories have been used in the field language teaching. Some experts use them as basic theories when teaching evolving language methods. It is known as the psycholinguistic approach. The psycholinguistic approach sees learning as cognitive individual process that occurs within the personality, and then goes into the social dimension. As an approach, there are several methods that have been developed based on the theories of psycholinguistics such as the natural method, the total physical response method, and the suggestopedia method. These methods apply the psycholinguistic principles of how a person acquires their native or first language (First language learning), learning their second or third language

(Second language learning), perceives language (linguistic perception) and produces language (language production).

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